

**CONGRUENCES FOR GENERALIZED FROBENIUS PARTITIONS
WITH AN ARBITRARILY LARGE NUMBER OF COLORS**

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Received: 6/5/13, Accepted: 12/27/13, Published: 1/22/14

Abstract

In his 1984 AMS Memoir, George Andrews defined the family of k -colored generalized Frobenius partition functions. These are enumerated by $c\phi_k(n)$ where $k \geq 1$ is the number of colors in question. In that memoir, Andrews proved (among many other things) that, for all $n \geq 0$, $c\phi_2(5n+3) \equiv 0 \pmod{5}$. Soon after, many authors proved congruence properties for various k -colored generalized Frobenius partition functions, typically with a small number of colors.

Work on Ramanujan-like congruence properties satisfied by the functions $c\phi_k(n)$ continues, with recent works completed by Baruah and Sarmah as well as the second author. Unfortunately, in all cases, the authors restrict their attention to small values of k . This is often due to the difficulty in finding a “nice” representation of the generating function for $c\phi_k(n)$ for large k . Because of this, no Ramanujan-like congruences are known where k is large. In this note, we rectify this situation by proving several infinite families of congruences for $c\phi_k(n)$ where k is allowed to grow arbitrarily large. The proof is truly elementary, relying on a generating function representation which appears in Andrews’ Memoir but has gone relatively unnoticed.

1. Introduction

In his 1984 AMS Memoir, George Andrews [2] defined the family of k -colored generalized Frobenius partition functions which are enumerated by $c\phi_k(n)$ where $k \geq 1$ is the number of colors in question. These combinatorial objects serve as a natural generalization of ordinary integer partitions. We provide a brief explanation here.

The Ferrers graph associated with a partition $\lambda_1 + \lambda_2 + \cdots + \lambda_r$ of n with $\lambda_i \geq \lambda_{i+1}$

is generally represented as a set of left-justified rows of dots where the i^{th} row contains λ_i dots. For example, the Ferrers graph of the partition $7+7+5+4+2+2$ is given by the following:

From here we consider the Frobenius symbol associated with an integer partition. Given the Ferrers graph of a partition, note that the rows of dots strictly to the right of the r diagonal elements can be enumerated to provide one strictly decreasing sequence of r nonnegative integers (the r^{th} row might be empty, producing a value of 0). The remaining dots strictly below the main diagonal can be enumerated by columns to provide a second strictly decreasing sequence of r nonnegative integers. The resulting two sequences are then written in the form of a two-rowed array. For example, the partition $7+7+5+4+2+2$ of 27 mentioned above is represented by the Frobenius symbol

$$\begin{pmatrix} 6 & 5 & 2 & 0 \\ 5 & 4 & 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}.$$

From here we can describe the generalized Frobenius partitions of n using k colors. Consider k copies of the nonnegative integers written j_i where $j \geq 0$ and $1 \leq i \leq k$. We then say that $j_i < l_m$ precisely when $j < l$ or $j = l$ and $i < m$. Moreover, j_i is equal to l_m if and only if $j = l$ and $i = m$.

Then $c\phi_k(n)$ counts the number of generalized Frobenius partitions of n under the conditions that the parts are “decreasing” (using the ordering above). Thus, for example, $c\phi_2(2) = 9$:

$$\begin{pmatrix} 1_1 \\ 0_1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 1_2 \\ 0_1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 1_1 \\ 0_2 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 1_2 \\ 0_2 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 0_1 \\ 1_1 \end{pmatrix} \\ \begin{pmatrix} 0_1 \\ 1_2 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 0_2 \\ 1_1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 0_2 \\ 1_2 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 0_2 & 0_1 \\ 0_2 & 0_1 \end{pmatrix}$$

Among many things, Andrews [2, Corollary 10.1] proved that, for all $n \geq 0$, $c\phi_2(5n + 3) \equiv 0 \pmod{5}$. Soon after, many authors proved similar congruence properties for various k -colored generalized Frobenius partition functions, typically for a small number of colors k . See, for example, [5, 6, 7, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 15].

In recent years, this work has continued. Baruah and Sarmah [3] proved a number of congruence properties for $c\phi_4$, all with moduli which are powers of 4. Motivated by this work of Baruah and Sarmah, the second author [14] further studied 4-colored

generalized Frobenius partitions and proved that for all $n \geq 0$, $c\phi_4(10n + 6) \equiv 0 \pmod{5}$.

Unfortunately, in all the works mentioned above, the authors restrict their attention to small values of k . This is often due to the difficulty in finding a “nice” representation of the generating function for $c\phi_k(n)$ for large k . Because of this, no Ramanujan–like congruences are known where k is large. The goal of this brief note is to rectify this situation by proving several infinite families of congruences for $c\phi_k(n)$ where k is allowed to grow arbitrarily large. The proof is truly elementary, relying on a generating function representation which appears in Andrews’ Memoir but has gone relatively unnoticed.

2. Our Congruence Results

We begin by noting the following generating function result from Andrews’ AMS Memoir [2, Equation (5.14)]:

Theorem 2.1. *For fixed k , the generating function for $c\phi_k(n)$ is the constant term (i.e., the z^0 term) in*

$$\prod_{n=0}^{\infty} (1 + zq^{n+1})^k (1 + z^{-1}q^n)^k.$$

Theorem 2.1 is the springboard that Andrews uses to find “nice” representations of the generating functions for $c\phi_k(n)$ for $k = 1, 2$, and 3 . Theorem 2.1 rarely appears in the works written by the various authors referenced above; however, it is extremely useful in proving the following theorem, the main result of this note.

Theorem 2.2. *Let p be prime and let r be an integer such that $0 < r < p$. If*

$$c\phi_k(pn + r) \equiv 0 \pmod{p}$$

for all $n \geq 0$, then

$$c\phi_{pN+k}(pn + r) \equiv 0 \pmod{p}$$

for all $N \geq 0$ and $n \geq 0$.

Proof. Assume p is prime and r is an integer such that $0 < r < p$. Thanks to Theorem 2.1, we note that the generating function for $c\phi_{pN+k}(n)$ is the constant term (i.e., the z^0 term) in

$$\prod_{n=0}^{\infty} (1 + zq^{n+1})^{pN+k} (1 + z^{-1}q^n)^{pN+k}. \tag{1}$$

Since p is prime, we know (1) is congruent, modulo p , to

$$\prod_{n=0}^{\infty} (1 + (zq^{n+1})^p)^N (1 + (z^{-1}q^n)^p)^N \prod_{n=0}^{\infty} (1 + zq^{n+1})^k (1 + z^{-1}q^n)^k \quad (2)$$

thanks to the binomial theorem. Note that the first product in (2) is a function of q^p and the second product is the product from which we obtain the generating function for $c\phi_k(n)$ thanks to Theorem 2.1. Since the first product is indeed a function of q^p , and since we wish to find the generating function dissection for $c\phi_k(pn + r)$ where $0 < r < p$, we see that if $c\phi_k(pn + r) \equiv 0 \pmod{p}$ for all $n \geq 0$, then $c\phi_{pN+k}(pn + r) \equiv 0 \pmod{p}$ for all $n \geq 0$. \square

Of course, once one knows a single congruence of the form

$$c\phi_k(pn + r) \equiv 0 \pmod{p}$$

for all $n \geq 0$, where p be prime and r is an integer such that $0 < r < p$, then one can write down an infinite family of congruences for an arbitrarily large number of colors with the same modulus p . We provide a number of such examples here.

Corollary 2.3. *For all $N \geq 0$ and for all $n \geq 0$,*

$$\begin{aligned} c\phi_{5N+1}(5n + 4) &\equiv 0 \pmod{5}, \\ c\phi_{7N+1}(7n + 5) &\equiv 0 \pmod{7}, \text{ and} \\ c\phi_{11N+1}(11n + 6) &\equiv 0 \pmod{11}. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. This corollary of Theorem 2.2 follows from the fact that $c\phi_1(n) = p(n)$ for all $n \geq 0$ as well as Ramanujan’s well-known congruences for $p(n)$ modulo 5, 7, and 11. \square

Corollary 2.4. *For all $N \geq 0$ and for all $n \geq 0$, $c\phi_{5N+2}(5n + 3) \equiv 0 \pmod{5}$.*

Proof. This corollary of Theorem 2.2 follows from Andrews [2, Corollary 10.1] where he proved that, for all $n \geq 0$, $c\phi_2(5n + 3) \equiv 0 \pmod{5}$. \square

Corollary 2.5. *For all $N \geq 1$ and all $n \geq 0$, $c\phi_{3N}(3n + 2) \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$.*

Proof. This corollary of Theorem 2.2 follows from Kolitsch’s work [9] where he proved that, for all $n \geq 0$, $c\phi_3(3n + 2) \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$. \square

One last comment is in order. It is also clear that one can combine corollaries like those above in order to obtain some truly unique-looking congruences. For example, we note the following:

Corollary 2.6. *For all $N \geq 0$ and all $n \geq 0$,*

$$c\phi_{1155N+1002}(1155n + 908) \equiv 0 \pmod{1155}.$$

Proof. The proof of this result follows from the Chinese Remainder Theorem and the fact that $1155 = 3 \times 5 \times 7 \times 11$ along with a combination of the corollaries mentioned above. \square

It is extremely gratifying to be able to explicitly identify such congruences satisfied by these generalized Frobenius partition functions.

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